

Graph-based Interpretable Anomaly Detection Framework for Network Slice Management in Beyond 5G Networks

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Abstract—5G and Beyond 5G systems are built with unprecedented scale, heterogeneity and programmability in mind, and come with features such as increased technological complexity (due to increased heterogeneity and abstraction); dynamic behavior of the network prompted by dynamic demand for new functionality and capacity extensions; variability and volume of network access (e.g., type and number of connections, diverse types of services and traffic patterns), etc. Therefore, one of the major requirements for the management of these systems is automation. Rather than having only local, segregated automation mechanisms (e.g., node self-configuration, SON, etc.), it is now agreed that automation is one of the main management features to be implemented for end-to-end proactive management. In this paper, we present a novel solution for supporting automated and proactive decision-making at the *network slice level* in 5G / Beyond 5G telecommunication systems. We propose a Graph-based Interpretable Anomaly Detection (GSIAD) framework that combines the use of Graph Convolutional Neural Networks with model correlations between multivariate network slice Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and forecasts individual time series using Recurrent Neural Networks/GRUs. The architecture also includes an anomaly detection mechanism based on probabilistic classification. This unsupervised approach helps network operators identify and explain features of the KPIs, leading to faster root cause analysis and enabling self-managed network slices. Our model was tested in a realistic 5G simulation and demonstrated 45.9% better accuracy when trained with a Graph CNN and Recurrent Neural Network compared to the GRU model.

Index Terms—Neural Network, eXplainable AI, Beyond 5G

I. INTRODUCTION

Network slicing is a fundamental concept in 5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) networks. While it increases the flexibility of the system in order to support different types of deployments and services, it also increases the complexity of the management solution many fold. Current standardisation directions have focused on centralised management of such virtualised systems, such a solution becoming extremely complex and hard to scale to the number of slices that are envisioned.

In line with new initiatives such as ZSM, a new slice management architecture was proposed, based on the decentralisation of its monitoring, analytics and decision functions, as well as focusing on automatic AI-driven management and orchestration [2].

Rather than a centralized solution, as it is considered by both ETSI NFV [3] and 3GPP management architectures [4], our project (MonB5G¹) has designed three decentralised components: Monitoring System (MS), Analytics Engine (AE) and Decision Engine (DE), which are deployed on the different entities taking part in the management process, i.e., MANO, OSS/BSS, NSMF, the in-slice management plane, distributing the management functions among these entities, in order to ensure a scalable management system.

The focus of this paper is on the AE, which is designed to analyze the status of network slices using telemetry data collected by the MS, predict slice KPIs and detect anomalies in KPI trends. Its outputs, i.e., the analysis results, are then reported to MonB5G DE as key indicators to learn from and infer actionable decisions to maintain and optimize the slice performance as defined in SLAs. AE exploits the MonB5G distributed architecture to push the analysis close to the data collection MS in each domain (i.e., RAN, Edge, Cloud), minimizing the need to transfer raw slice performance and configuration data across the different network domains and slices.

The end-to-end slice KPIs to be predicted by the AE have been defined in line with standards specifications [5] and reflect the slice performance, including for example upstream / downstream throughput for Network Slice Instance (NSI), average end-to-end uplink/downlink delay, virtualized resource utilization per NSI, etc. Compared to KPI prediction in older systems, we take into account 5G characteristics that are important when implementing a slice level AE. The number of slices, as well as the amount of data collected when automatic slice redeployment is enabled, are important factors that affect the effectiveness and efficiency of the AE so a scalable solution must be developed.

Additionally, networks are affected by many factors, and using isolated performance monitoring metrics is no longer sufficient to reveal the true cause of network slice issues. Taking also into account the very diverse service requirements in 5G and Beyond 5G (e.g., enhanced mobile broadband

¹<https://www.monb5g.eu/>

eMBB vs. ultra-reliable low-latency communication URLLC), a deeper understanding of the causes requires a deeper investigation of influencing factors, which are only known to subject matter experts. These factors must be considered when making automatic optimization decisions. Therefore, we propose an intelligent system that can consider the influencing factors in our predictions.

In this paper, we focus on: (1) The importance of slice level KPIs predicted by graph based representation learning method applied in conjunction with recurrent neural networks (RNN). (2) This solution coupled with an interpretable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) - based solution enables a wider adoption of automated management by telecom operators. The proposed framework (G5IAD) provides explanations (e.g. what combination of KPI values impacted the slice latency KPI) that can be used by the experts and/or by a flexible DE for maintaining slice SLAs, by using direct information from the interpretable method, compared to methods that compute and compare outcomes for all possible actions.

The key contributions of this paper are as follows: (1) The definition of *G5IAD* Reference Architecture based on a novel graph and RNN architecture in multivariate correlated time series data to improve slice level KPI predictions; (2) The design and implementation of an interpretable framework for network slice KPI Anomaly Detection based on sequential anomaly detection; (3) The testing of the proposed framework in a realistic 5G simulation before deployment on the real MonB5G platform. The results of the testing show an improved accuracy by 45.9% compared to the classical GRU model.

II. RELATED WORK AND BACKGROUND

The use of ML in telecom network management has expanded with each new telecom generation [1], with more complex models envisioned for Beyond 5G networks. The complexity and scale of these networks points to new models that can learn and adapt with network & service requirements.

Our work draws on ML and XAI previous research, such as the work in [6] where multiple linear regression based models for application KPIs are investigated, with the final goal of determining useful characteristics of an application’s traffic. The emergence of Graph Neural Network based methods have gained importance and allow network research to explore to process an arbitrary number of neighboring nodes for each node. Motivated by this, the authors in [7] proposed a novel graph neural network model which learns insights from slicing - enabled networks represented by the graph structure to predict E2E latency.

Additionally, the field of eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) studies methods [8] to provide explanations of the decisions taken by black box models, such as deep neural networks. The authors in [9] demonstrated the Cluster Characterized Architecture (CCA) in telecom networks to illustrate

the interpretability of anomalous network data using SHAP and subspace clustering.

To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first to cover a few key aspects of the application of interpretable results to telecom networks, such as: evaluation of multivariate KPIs to the quality of the anomalies in slice KPI predictions, advantages of providing an Interpretable framework (highlighting contributing factors) which impacts the decision on slice optimisation, and how well predictive models help the network consider service SLAs when making a new decision.

III. THE MONB5G ARCHITECTURE

The MonB5G architecture is based on the concept of distributed MS/AE/DE components that collaborate to deliver automatic scalable slice management in a 5G/B5G system, in line with the ETSI ZSM [10] requirements and vision of distributed multi-layer AI-driven control [2].

Fig. 1. MonB5G Architecture

Fig. 1 gives a high-level overview of the distributed MS/AE/DE per domain/slice. The MS is the entity responsible for collecting metrics from the systems that the DE controls. The MS communicates with AE and DE for passing the metrics in a flexible way, so that the processing in AE & DE does not compromise the granularity with which MS can retrieve monitoring data from the controlled systems. Thus, it is the MS (depending on its capabilities, the amount of information, as well as the granularity set by the External User Interface (EUI)) that defines how fast the data is sampled.

The AE reads the monitoring information from a stored Common Online Memory Store (COMS) (via Kafka bus) to pre-process it (e.g., perform predictions) before making it available to the DE. The AE can also read the information directly from the MS, but this is likely to be used in more selective cases, where some synchronization is required. Similarly, DE reads input from the COMS.

The next Section focuses on the AE architecture, while later sections explain the design, implementation and evaluation aspects related to the AE.

IV. G5IAD FRAMEWORK

Multivariate time-series analysis is an important model that simultaneously analyzes multiple measurements to study the behavior of time-dependent data, and forecasts future values depending on the history of variations in the data. Fig.2 illustrates the AE workflow which incorporates the input data points from MS and is further trained using graph theory to produce the slice KPI predictions and perform fault detection on predictions. In the following sections, we introduce the MonB5G Analytics Engine and design an Interpretation Framework, as shown in Fig. 2 that predicts and then detects the anomalies in the slice KPIs.

Fig. 2. MonB5G Architecture

A. Graph Theory based Representation learning - AE prediction model

Graph Neural Networks models the relationship between a set of objects (nodes or vertices V) and their connections/interrelationships (given by a set of edges E linking the respective nodes/vertices) in non Euclidean space (data points, which may or may not have the same underlying domain, i.e. same graph structure defined by an adjacency matrix). We propose a combination of graph convolutional and recurrent connections that uses multiple time series as an input to the network. This approach helps in capturing the spatial and temporal relationship among the network attributes in a slice. Our model receives x_t , the time series input KPIs (e.g., CPU, RAM, Bandwidth, Storage) as input, along with sequences of slice KPI values (e.g., slice latency).

We define a graph as $G = (V, x, E)$ where V is the set of nodes; $x \in R^N$ is a vector for every vertex, which contains one or more attributes about the vertex; E represents the set of edges. An edge $e_{ij} = (v_i, v_j)$ connects nodes v_i and v_j . A common way to represent and store a graph is with an Adjacency matrix $A \in R^{N \times N}$ where A_{ij} records the connection between the vertices and $N = |V|$, is a square matrix such $A_{ij} = 1$ if there is an edge from node v_i to node v_j , and 0 otherwise. The computational efficiency formula to calculate the graph convolution is defined as:

$$g_\theta * x \approx D^{-1/2} A D^{-1/2} x \theta \quad (1)$$

$$A = D^{-1/2} A D^{-1/2} \quad (2)$$

where $D \in R^{N \times N}$ represents the diagonal degree matrix, denoted by $D_{ij} = \sum_j A_{ij}$, $\theta \in R$ and the adjacency matrix A does not contain the connection of vertex itself.

The work in this proposed framework adopts the hybrid graph theory and Recurrent Neural Network based architecture to learn meaningful network information in an unsupervised manner. To discover hidden associations among network nodes (representing the input features), a graph learning layer computes the graph adjacency matrix, which is later used as an input to all graph convolution modules. The graph learning layer learns a graph adjacency matrix which captures the hidden relationships among the multitude of network slices. This is then fed into the Gated Recurrent Units to capture the temporal dependencies. We draw on the advantages of both these methods to model both temporal and intra-feature dependencies.

A variant of Recurrent Neural Networks knows as GRU was proposed by Chung et al. [11] to solve the problem of vanishing gradient. The functionality of GRU is almost similar to LSTM, but with the difference of no separate memory cells. Experimentally GRU models converges faster when compared to an LSTM neural network model. GRU's architecture is internally simpler and consists of an update gate and a reset gate defined as:

$$z_t = \sigma(W_z x_t + U_z h_{t-1}) \quad (3)$$

Where σ is non-linear activation function, x_t and h_{t-1} denotes the input and the hidden states at time "t" and "t-1" respectively. W_z and U_z represents the weight matrices been learned.

$$r_t = \sigma(W_r x_t + U_r h_{t-1}) \quad (4)$$

The candidate activation \tilde{h} is computed as:

$$\tilde{h} = \tanh(W x_t + U(r_t \odot h_{t-1})) \quad (5)$$

where r_t is reset gate and \odot is an element-wise multiplication.

The sequences for the input model, as shown in Fig. 2 are passed through the Recurrent Neural Network GRU layers, while the correlation matrices are processed by GCNs. Here the initial node features (time series data points) are provided as an input to the GCN and then, the node embeddings are computed by applying the series of convolutional modules. We first use the historical time series data as an input and the GCN is used to capture the topological structure of network to obtain the relational dependencies. Second, the obtained time series with relational dependencies are input into the gated recurrent units where the units capture the temporal features. Finally, we get results through the fully connected layer to predict the slice KPIs.

For our training, we split the training and testing data as 70-30 ratio. A Batch Normalization layer was applied, which acts as a regularization and greatly improves the overall model performance. The predictions are retrieved at the end. The errors of the model are calculated as Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) on test data, defined as:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - x'_i)^2} \quad (6)$$

B. Fault Management Probabilistic Model

Fault Management has been a fundamental part of network management, included in the FCAPS operations (Fault, Configuration, Accounting, Performance and Security). It aims to detect & eliminate malfunctions that have occurred in the monitored systems to prevent the degradation of services. In 5G/B5G networks, because of the high degree of flexibility and change in the network, faults must be carefully considered within the particular context in which they appear [1].

Here we leverage Recurrent Neural Networks and Hidden Markov Model to estimate the probability of a sequence [12] (e.g., *sliceLatency* KPI) occurring using these probability distributions. Note that $p(x_i|x_{1:i-1})$ is the probability of the integer x_i occurring after the sequence $x_{1:i-1}$. A language model for sequences specifies a probability distribution for the next in a sequence given the set of previous sequences. Using a training set of well-known normal sequences, the probabilistic neural network is then trained to generate this probability distribution as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Probabilistic Classifier for Predicting Anomalous Sequences

C. Interpretation Framework

Most Deep Neural Networks are a "black box" that cannot provide easily interpretable insights into the relationship between input and output. Particularly, when there is high dimensional data and multiple layers in the neural network, there is a need for a method (post-hoc, after training) that can be used to provide the interpretability of models on the datasets where the ground-truth of interpretation results is not available.

The Deep Explainer SHAP function takes as input the model, an instance of anomalous test x and a set of background instances. For a particular feature x'_i it calculates a set of SHAP values which measures the importance of each of the

Algorithm 1 Anomalous Sequence Interpretation

Input: trainData - Background instances

x - (trainData, 5,000)

model - trained model

Anomalousdf - Predicted anomalies

row - Anomalous sequence to be explained

Output: Anomalies Contributions

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1: procedure ANOMALIES
2:   filterdf  $\leftarrow$  Anomalousdf
3:   topFeatures  $\leftarrow$  sortfilterdf[Desc,allFeatures]
4:   topFeatures  $\leftarrow$  topFeatures.Transpose
5:   for feature in topFeatures.index: do
6:     weights, bias  $\leftarrow$  model.getweights()
7:     featureIndex  $\leftarrow$  trainData.index[feature]
8:     updatedWeights[featureIndex]  $\leftarrow$  [0] * weights
9:     model.setWeights  $\leftarrow$  (updatedWeights,bias)
10:    allFeatures, shapValue, inputValue  $\leftarrow$ 
        DeepExplainer(model,x)
11:    forcePlot  $\leftarrow$  featureIndex, shapValue, row
12:    summaryPlot  $\leftarrow$  shapValue, row
13:  end for
14:  print topFeatures
15: end procedure

```

features x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n in predicting x'_i . The complete implementation process is described in Algorithm 1. The pseudo code explains how SHapley values are being interpreted to explain the anomalies using SHAP output. For each feature in the list of top features, we set the model weights and use Deep SHAP explainer to calculate the SHapley values. The Deep Explainer SHapley function outputs allFeatures, shapValue and inputValue for anomalous input sequence.

V. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

As mentioned in the Fig. 1 (MonB5G architecture), the AE and DE work together for optimising network E2E average slice latency. The AE is deployed in a container as a Python script. The AE can be deployed quickly as a stateless container at any node of the network, eliminating the single point of failure. The DE is instantiated as a docker container in the cloud and it is responsible for the VNF orchestration of the main slice. The two modules communicate through a Kafka bus as depicted in Fig. 4. The AE receives a row of dataset at the predefined time interval of 60 seconds. The AE responds to the DE with a slice KPI prediction at the next interval.

A. Dataset Description

The generated dataset includes computing and network performance metrics, such as the number of available CPU cores, memory, disk storage and link bandwidth utilization for each domain, per slice. The metrics are measured periodically at a predefined time frame. The generated datasets employed by the AE are based on a real multi-slice SDN and NFV-enabled

Fig. 4. Cloud Implementation of the proposed solution

topology. The simulated infrastructure topology is a multi-domain variation of the *2005 Nordu European Network*, from The Internet Topology Zoo dataset [14]. It is composed of 6 computing domains located in 6 different northern European cities. Each domain includes 3 server racks with 16 CPU cores, 64 GBs of RAM memory and 1TB of storage, all available for VM hosting.

In our study, the slice latency KPI was calculated based on our simulated environment (custom-made OpenAI Gym). The destination VM is the VM that provides to the user the service required. This can encapsulate services such as web server, database access, etc., categorized into several groups depending on their requirements (e.g., RAM, number of cores, storage, etc.). For a real deployment, we note that a model for calculating latency must be devised and used (e.g., either using testing UEs and / or considering a model tested on the network), while the computational KPIs used (storage, memory, CPU) are measured through the NFVI APIs. These computational resources are measured on the path from the UE to the VM providing the service (i.e., in the nodes where the slice is being deployed). In our framework, we used a decentralised monitoring system, that provides the input KPIs needed for the prediction and anomaly detection. A centralised monitoring system would provide information related to all slices and some filtering would need to be in place.

B. Parameter Initialization

In the experiment, we set the following hyperparameters as, learning rate to $3e-4$, window size of 24, batch size to 32 and the training epoch to 100. We choose the number of hidden units from [64,100,250] and analyze the change of prediction accuracy. A set of 14,652 data points were generated by the simulator as an input data to train for referenced architecture, and further slice KPI predictions been used for anomaly detection for providing an interpretable anomaly explainer. The hyperparameters were selected through a method of hit and trial given multiple combinations to best fit the model. The model optimizes the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss using Adam optimizer, uses early callback mechanism stopping with patience of 15 and relu activation function.

C. Performance Evaluation & Candidate Anomaly Detection

Fig. 5 represents the performance of the compared algorithms trained using multivariate KPIs to predict *sliceLatency*

KPI (normalized values) in a multivariate network data environment. We show the loss curve compared to different models, and observe that the model with Graph GCN generalises well over the training data as compared to the other models as shown in Table I. The key idea behind GNNs is to aggregate feature information from the nodes local neighbors via neural networks.

TABLE I
ALGORITHM COMPARISON

Algorithm	MSE
Neural Network	0.030909
CNN	0.032368
GRU	0.036695
GRU CNN	0.032652
Graph GCN with GRU	0.022974

Fig. 5. Prediction Comparison among Different Methods

Our results show that our AE architecture (joint learning framework based on GCN combined with GRU based architecture trained using network slice KPI data) helps to optimize the modelling of KPI data. The trained probabilistic model detects anomalies in *sliceLatency* KPI. As shown in Table II, the time taken for GRU based model (best tuned model with regularization technique, batch size = 32, Dropout 30% and callback mechanism technique) is approximately **20.42%** faster than LSTM due to faster convergence in training. When given an anomalous KPI sequences, the model detects the anomalies with lower probability scores.

We detect the candidate anomalies in the network slice KPI data using an unsupervised technique as the labeled data is not normally available. We detect anomalies in the test samples by calculating the robust Z-scores based on probability scores, defined as:

TABLE II
MODEL EVALUATION

RMSE	RNN Units	Time taken to Train (sec)
4.296	LSTM with 200 units	433
4.320	GRU with 200 units	410
3.50	GRU with 250 units + Regularizer	396

$$Z_{score} = \frac{0.6745 \times (x_i - \tilde{x})}{MAD} \quad (7)$$

where 0.6475 is the 0.75th quartile of the standard normal distribution, x_i the data points (MSE), \tilde{x} the median and MAD denotes the median absolute deviation. A Z-score greater than the threshold value (5) is determined as an anomaly (anomalous KPI sequence).

D. Interpretation

For the purpose of evaluation, anomalous sequences were sorted based on the probability scores and one of the top anomalous KPI sequence was further analysed.

Fig. 6. SHAP values to explain the contributing factors for Anomalies for sliceLatency KPI.

We review local interpretation results generated by SHAP (normalized values) as shown in Fig. 6. The Deep Explainer outputs features, SHAP values and input value for anomalous sequences as explained in Algorithm 1. To get a representation of the relationships between features for these anomalous KPI sequences, we obtained the most contributing feature(s) for sliceLatency KPI (in our case, the top impacting feature was **bandwidth**). This information is taken as input by the operators and / or the DE.

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this paper we present our design, implementation and evaluation of an Analytics Engine for distributed network slice management. We proposed a clear architecture for the AE, based on graph GCN with GRU model, which encapsulates both temporal and cross-KPI dependencies, which are essential in a scalable 5G and Beyond 5G system. The architecture also includes an anomaly detector model to improve slice KPI predictions. Additionally, we often see that the ability to explain the predictions is essential for added stakeholder trust and improved automation. For this reason, we include a SHAP method and show that it fits our goals well, providing feature analysis information for an unsupervised type of learning on a data set with multiple types of dependencies, as opposed to methods based on decision trees that imply the use of labelled

data on limited data sets. Additionally, our model scales well with the number of KPIs considered for the input, as opposed to LSTM models where we see exponential increases as we increase the number of parameters. Our results show 45% improved accuracy over classical GRU. The model proposed works per slice and it can be generalised to slices with similar characteristics. Future work involves the integration of our AE with DE, leading to proactive automated ML-based orchestration in 5G/B5G networks. Our testing will also be extended to a real 5G platform provided by one of the partners in the project.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is funded by the EU H2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 871780 (MonB5G).

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